

The Impact of COVID-19 on Tourism and Hospitality Industry: A Qualitative Investigation in Pakistan

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Abstract

The tourism and hospitality industry provides its various effects on economic, social, and political sides of any country. Also, it retains a great importance in the overall economic development of the country. The year 2019 was the triumphant year for the Tourism industry in Pakistan, and its contribution rate to Pakistan's GDP was 5.9% in 2019. However, in the year 2020, because of COVID-19 pandemic, the country's GDP has been declined significantly. The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the sectors which is highly effected by COVID-19 pandemic. The data were collected from the WHO website, existing literature, and online surveys. Findings revealed that the COVID-19 pandemic led to the rapid shut down in cities and states across the boundary of Pakistan and negatively affected to all the sectors of tourism and hospitality industry like airline operations, hotel sector, travel agencies, tourist inflow, and entertainment sector of the country. The finding disclosed that the rapid increase in COVID-19 pandemic cancelled all the hotel and tourism bookings which lead to unemployment and revenue loss. The resulting loss of the potential revenue negatively affected the Pakistan's economy and increased the poverty line. The aim of this study was to contribute to the existing literature by exploring the impact of COVID-19 on tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan, and to identify the economic resilience scheme that would be emerged because of this pandemic.

Keywords: Covid-19, Tourism, Hospitality, Pakistan

1. Introduction

The disaster coronavirus is spread in about 90% of the world countries and territories which is 196 in number almost in every island across the world (Choi & Bum, 2020). The Covid-19 harms the travel and tour industry. Tourists play a key role in transferring the coronavirus between the regional communities (Peter Jones, 2020). The initial studies show that the travel restrictions are helpful and huge effective intervention in the starting and late phase of the pandemic, to reduce the spread and control the transference rate in communities (Kyriakidou & Maroudas, 2010).

After that, every country is tried to stop the spreading of this virus, which spread from human to human. The virus has a major effect on the economic activities of the whole countries i.e., to make it slows down, due to the many and most of the world countries by the semi or complete lockdown (Nguyen & Schinckus, 2020).

The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the sectors which is highly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. Covid-19 pandemic results, to the rapid shut down in cities and states across the boundary of Pakistan and negatively affected to all the sectors of tourism and hospitality industry like airlines operations, hotel sector, travel agencies, tourist inflow, and entertainment sector of the country (Ozili & Arun, 2020). While 2019 was the successful year for the tourism industry in Pakistan, and its contribution rate to Pakistan's GDP was 5.9 % and leads the economy towards a better way (Covid-19 and Pakistan's economy, 2020). This pandemic changed tourists' spending patterns and consumer behavior, which worst affects the economy and GDP of Pakistan. Due to this, a huge revenue loss causes a decline in demand and unemployment of service staff (Huang, 2020).

Besides, another big problem is that both the hospitality and tourism industries do not have recovery plans, which help them regain their market share and help them survive in the long run. The theory says that such companies do not survive in the long run who does not have strategic plans (Amante & Balmer, 2020).

All the fallouts are still unknown, possible outcomes and solutions are yet to be determined. Tourist behavior is unpredictable because they were feared due to disaster. Due to this situation, the tourism industry is affected negatively and travel companies bear a huge revenue loss and as a result, it hospitality industry falls which is directly related to tourism (Gallen, 2020).

Therefore, the present research is important as it aims to understand and reveal the unknowns that occurred in the tourism and hospitality sector in Pakistan during the Covid-19 pandemic. Clarifying these issues can also shed light on the tourism and hospitality sectors in other countries, as a similar situation is experienced all over the world.

Covid-19 pandemic created different situations far from other problems that lived in the tourism and hospitality industry and its feature are diverse from previous problematic situations; so, it can be defined as an anomaly. As Thomas Khun explained in his book, anomalies are incubators of the change of previous paradigm (Khun, 1960) but they can also be considered as factors that are due to social and economic structures. These processes are the formation paradigm in this regard (Elena, 2020). The situation created by the Covid-19 pandemic process inevitably reminds us of the changing foundations of history scenes even though its name and era are different. Just as the past pandemic

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epidemics have been the catalyst for the destruction of feudalism, the spread of colonialism, the lying of the foundations of commerce and capitalism, the emergence of development. This anomaly has played the role of embracing modern technology, emerging the increased efforts of science and medicine for new inventions that determined their fate in the paradigmatic change. The Covid-19 pandemic has similar characteristics (Genc & Akyurek, 2020).

Accordingly, the main aim of the present study is to determine how and to what extent Covid-19 has had an impact on the tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan. As another contribution, this research aims to contribute to the existing literature by assessing the impact of Covid-19 on the tourism and hospitality industry, identifying the economic resilience to deal with this anomalous process. In addition, it is a practical contribution that understanding the dynamics of the anomaly process that occurs with the pandemic, in general, is beneficial not only for Pakistan but also for other countries in general. Besides, the results are expected to show the behavior of tourists regarding economic conditions during and after this pandemic.

2. Theoretical Background

To understand the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the tourism and hospitality industry, initially explaining the tourist behavior and situation during pandemic generally in the literature may give a clear sense that why and how tourist behavior is crucial during the crises situation. Most of the researchers agreed that the tourists' behavior comprises both internal and external factors. Internal factors include personal preferences and internal characteristics and external factors include preferences and decisions (Maslow, 1943). Ayrca, safety is one of the important factors for tourists. Consumers predict the possible outcomes that would arise as the result of their decision about product selection, so consumers always develop a strategy to choose a less-risk factor product or its alternative. Decision-making of the consumer is very crucial about uncertainty (Khan, 2020). Consumers are attracted only if safe and suitable services are provided which they desired and wanted (Yousaf & Amin, 2018). Scientific management based on “consumer behavior” studies is one of the theories by Brain T. Ratchford for consumer behavior; it is indeed a search of psychological theory that is directly interlinked with the beliefs of behavior and concerned with the purchasing, market capitalism, and perception of consumer behavior.

2.1. Theoretical Perspective on Consumer Behavior and Marketing Development Strategy

As a broad theoretical framework, motivation theory is not concerned with behavior only. The theory of consumer behavior is primarily concerned with the psychology and sociological aspects but by new economists; there are some new implications in the theory which concerned with the behavior towards demand, price, and characteristics of the product which examined biologically, culturally, and situationally (Ratchford, 1975). Human behavior is not automatic, demands and rules are externally imposed the forces to change behavior accordingly and most of the time they are driven by intimate goals. The first implication is directly concerned with the preferences towards the attributes and the differentiation and is used to measure the multidimensional scales and multi-attributes to explain the preferences (Ratchford, 1975). The second major implication of the theory is the activities of the consumer. Consumers always make a combination of products to satisfy his/her demand. So the consumer behavior is directly related to preferences and decision-making towards selection. That's why this theory felt appropriate for this study (Ratchford, 1975).

2.2. Marketing Development Strategy

With the usage of the market development strategy, almost all the tourist industries can recover their market. Where “market development” is an expansion strategy, that recognizes and creates the new market section for the existing or current product. It is basically the strategy that develops the existing market with the existing offerings means the hospitality and tour industry seeks new customers with the existing offerings, the overall effort is done to boost the revenues. So, the tourist and hospitality industry can generate a new market for present/current or existing tourist offerings. For the development of the marketing strategy, there is a need to elaborate the existing strategic recommendation, researchers need to do a SWOT analysis (strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threat) and strategic planning matrix also used to analyze the current market situation to recommend the suitable strategy for marketing development (Rachmat, 2020). Market penetration and product development strategy are also important for the strategy of marketing development.

3. Current Study

3.1. Data Collection and Empirical Setting

In the current study, the field of tourism and hospitality is selected as the empirical setting in which data is collected and hospitality companies in city Lahore of Pakistan. Until now there are few studies available in Covid-19 pandemic research(Kaushal & Srivastava, 2021) which are related to specific fields. However, these few studies have selected tourism and hospitality companies as participants. Although tourism and hospitality contributed towards GDP

significantly but how this contribution has been declined due to the Covid-19 pandemic is an important question. Since tourism and hospitality is an industry that contributes towards GDP significantly, it also has importance towards the economic development of the country.

The current study on the tourism and hospitality industry and the Covid-19 pandemic highlight the many issues and opportunities including decline in demand and patronage, unemployment of service staff, revenue loss, travel restrictions and social distancing, economic recovery plans, and preparations to cope with issues (Solomon, 2020).

The tourism and hospitality industry provides various effects on the economic, social, and political sides of any country. Also, it retains great importance in the overall economic development of the country. The year 2019 was the triumphant year for the Tourism industry in Pakistan, and its contribution rate to Pakistan's GDP was 5.9% in 2019. However, in the year 2020, because of the Covid-19 pandemic, the country's GDP has been declined significantly. The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the sectors which is highly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic (NASEEM, 2021).

3.2. Research Design

The qualitative method is used to investigate the social and cultural aspects. While investigating the cultural and social experiences, the response of participants is much important. It provides in-depth and well-off information about a particular topic (Akyurek, 2020). In order to examine the factors affecting the tourism and hospitality industry which include decline in demand and patronage, revenue loss, unemployment of service staff during the Covid-19 pandemic, I have conducted semi-structured interviews to acquire in-depth and well of information. This information also enriches my knowledge in different ways which include personal, contextual, and relational characteristics. Tourists' behavior was important to investigate the impact of Covid-19 effects on the tourism and hospitality industry and the government of Pakistan also played very important role during this pandemic. So, this impact and thorough examination could only be conducted only employing the qualitative research method.

The aim of my qualitative research is to investigate the impact of Covid-19 on the tourism and hospitality industry in-depth in Pakistan. A semi-structured interview was conducted which contains detailed questions to get data in-depth.

3.3. The Research Questions

Because the Covid-19 pandemic is an anomaly, its effects on human beings and organizations' lives need to be understood. However, there is very little study examining the adverse effects of the Covid-19 pandemic until now. In this regard, the main inquiry of this research is in this way: There is a need to understand how the pandemic affects the tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan. It is not possible to explore what dynamics are changing in the industry and what will emerge in the future for this industry without doing qualitative analysis. In the light of this perspective, we asked the semi-structured research questions below:

- What is happening in the tourism and hospitality industry due to the Covid-19 pandemic?
- How Covid-19 pandemic affected the tourism and hospitality industry?
- What will be the future of the industry after this Covid-19 pandemic is over?
- After understanding the problems of the current situation, what might be the solutions to the problems?

3.4. Interview procedure

Several questions were asked in the semi-structured interview based on the following research questions: Is there any decline in demand and patronage in the tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan? In the same direction, have they got revenue loss during the Covid19 pandemic? Also, what is the situation of the unemployment rate of service staff? How travel restrictions and social distancing are affecting the tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan? Have they got any strategic plans to deal with the pandemic conditions in the industry? Also, have they got any economic recovery plans? Are there any opportunities after the pandemic is over? Have they any preparation to get the advantage? These research questions were designed to understand and explore the current pandemic situation especially in the tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan. The research may shed light on which dynamics the problems affect by explaining these questions' answers. In this way, ideas might be developed on solutions to improve the pandemic conditions in terms of the tourism and hospitality industry, and plans might be organized and implemented.

The questions asked in the interview were based on existing literature and evaluated the impact of Covid-19 particularly and generally in the tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan. The interview questions will serve to find out the research questions' answers.

The interview was conducted face to face and also via phone call which was recorded safely and later on transcripts were prepared. The recorded data was reviewed many times to get the clear content of the data by two different expert researchers. The interview questions are included in the appendix.

3.5. Data analysis strategy

In the qualitative method, thematic analysis was used to analyze and interpret the raw data collected from the semi-structured interviews. While employing the thematic analysis on raw data, all the descriptions, analysis, and reporting

of the data are based on the themes. The thematic analysis enables the researcher to analyze and organize data in a rich and appropriate way (Akyurek, 2020). The data was collected in semi-structured interviews. It was recorded via phone calls and transcripts were prepared. After it, all of the written document was read several times to get the clear content of the texts. Open coding was used for coding the data without using any existing coding framework. Prepared codes were categorized into themes and sub-themes and then interpreted through the relevant theories. Two expert researchers analyzed the data independently at different times. After analysis, results were gathered in the same place and compared. The results of both researchers were very close to each other. They discussed and agreed on the results.

3.6. Sampling for interviews

Sampling is defined as, “to collect the necessary data according to the research objectives, correct data sources is determined”. For sampling, the purposive sampling technique is used in the current study. Purposive sampling technique is a type of non-probability sampling which is the most appropriate way to collect the certain domain from professionals of the required field. To increase the creditability and transferability of the study, sampling strategy is determined. In this study, the target population is tourism and hospitality companies. For this population, tourism and hospitality companies have been chosen from Lahore city of Pakistan. Tourism companies were the potential participants. Researchers were reached towards them through personal contact. Invitation of the meeting was sent to them and interviews were conducted of only those companies which accepted the invitation. The interview was conducted through phone calls because of strict lockdown conditions. All the phones calls were made face to face via WhatsApp. All of them were recorded and brief notes were prepared.

The trustworthiness of qualitative research depends upon the observing skills of the researcher and the available qualified data collected from participant's during interviews. The credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability of qualitative research can be shown as; the data was collected in one month and good interaction has been achieved with interviewees during interviews.

3.7. Interviewee profile

The participants consist of 68% male and 32% female in the current research. The average age of females was 35 and the age of males was 45. Of the 20-person sample, 10 were service personnel working in senior positions in tourism companies, 5 were tourists, and the remaining 5 were unemployed due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

4. Discussion

As seen in table 1, findings that are collected through semi-structured interviews will be discussed through qualitative research and existing literature to conclude the research in a meaningful way. Interpretation of the findings will be presented in this chapter. Future recommendations and limitations will also be discussed after this. At last, a brief summary of the current study will be presented in form of conclusion.

The aim of this study is to contribute to the existing literature by evaluating the impact of Covid-19 on the tourism and hospitality industry and to identify the economic resilience in Pakistan to cope with this anomaly situation. It is also important for the tourism and hospitality industry to understand what is happening in the industry due to the Covid-19 pandemic and how it is affected the industry. What will be the future of the industry after this covid-19 pandemic is over? After understanding the problems of the current situation, there is a need to find out the solutions to the problems because the situation is an anomaly. Not much is known about ongoing and ever-changing circumstances (Nashirah, 2020).

In the empirical setting, the field of tourism and hospitality is selected in which data is collected from tourism and hospitality companies in the city Lahore of Pakistan. First semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 people working at the senior level in tourism and hospitality companies. These interviews were conducted to highlight the current condition of the Tourism and hospitality industry in Pakistan besides how was their experience based on Covid-19 during the pandemic and how they explained the current situation of the tourism and hospitality industry in resulting of Covid-19 pandemic. During examining the qualitative research, it was seen that the respondents were in senior positions and playing a significant role in the companies. The tourism and hospitality industry is an important contributor to Pakistan's economy (Abdul & Muhammad, 2020).

Until now there are few studies available in Covid-19 pandemic research (Kaushal & Srivastava, 2021) which is related to the specific fields. However, these few studies have selected tourism and hospitality companies as participants. Although tourism and hospitality contributed towards GDP significantly, the how this contribution has been declined due to the Covid-19 pandemic is an important question. Since tourism and hospitality is an industry that contributed towards GDP significantly, it also has importance for the economic development of the country (Solomon, 2020).

As discussed in the existing literature; tourism is the temporary movement of people from their residence to the workplace and on leisure trips and it also includes all the activities which facilitate the people during the course of their travel from moving place to the destination. Tourism is specifically dependent upon the accommodations which

are available at the destinations of the tourism. Accommodations play a significant role in the development of the tourism industry in the country. Tourism plays a significant role in the economic, social, and psychological development of the country. It also promotes the culture of the host country towards the world. It also supports the betterment of the living standards of rural and urban sides of the country of the tourists have the different effects and it also causes a tax revenue for the local country. The tourism and hospitality industry comprises different departments which are interlinked with each other. Tourism and hospitality are made up of travel agencies, airline operation companies, hotels, resorts, eating points, restaurants, the entertainment sector, etc (Jaffar, 2021).

Human behavior depends upon psychology which changes according to the situation. During this pandemic, tourists' behavior diverts towards fear, health consciousness and they preferred to stay at home and quarantine. All the bookings and leisure trips were canceled which cause a severe decline in demand and patronage in the tourism and hospitality industry because of strict lockdown imposed by states all over the world. This disaster contributed negatively and caused a low down on the demand in the industry (Nashirah, 2020).

In addition, according to 2011 stats, the tourism and hospitality industry generated 3.4 million employment opportunities which are 5.7% of overall employment and the industry contributed about 86 billion towards the export of Pakistan. With the passage of time, it has significantly increased. The year 2019 was the triumphant year for the Tourism industry in Pakistan, and its contribution rate to Pakistan's GDP was 5.9% in 2019. The rapid development of this sector causes competitive economic development, which leads to the reduction of the poverty line increases employment opportunities, revenues, and also increases in the foreign exchange earnings which are employment opportunities (Abdul & Muhammad, 2020). However, in the year 2020, because of the Covid-19 pandemic, the country's GDP has been declined significantly, The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the sectors which is highly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic which causes a revenue loss of the owners. The existing literature is also consistent with this existing literature (Abdul & Muhammad, 2020).

However, the current situation is categorized as what is happening in the industry due to the Covid-19 pandemic and how it is affected the industry. What will be the future of the industry after this Covid-19 pandemic is over? After understanding the problems of the current situation, there is a need to find out the solutions to the problems because the situation is an anomaly and not much is known about ongoing and ever-changing circumstances (Vikrant & Sidharth, 2021).

Participants described that due to continuing lockdown, all the operations of the tourism and hospitality industry were closed. The situation was novel. Nobody knew how to deal with such a situation. There was a large number of employees were working in the sectors. The future of the pandemic was uncertain and due to continue actual and potential losses, owners said goodbye to most of their service staff, and 25000 families were affected except for employees who were working in high positions. The impact of the Covid-19 on the tourism and hospitality industry was severe. Because of it, the service staff was sent on vacations and temporal and contractual employees were terminated. Many of the organizations have taken loans from the banks and financial institutions to pay their expenses because of potential and revenue loss. This is also supported by existing literature (Vikrant & Sidharth, 2021).

In addition according to previous studies, companies would take advantage of the opportunities, by learning more than one skill, making plans according to the situation, need to digitalize more the business processes and uplift the related skills of the staff and workers and make multiple sources of income for financial stability because it is not a time to rely on one source of income or skill. This is also supported by the previous study. The strategic planform the current situation is that hotels need to change their operating patterns. When Covid-19 comes to a global, pandemic situation, no plan can fully work to deal, except waiting for vaccines to become available in abundance throughout the world, however as a workaround extensive training and awareness of hospitality and tourism industry related people can minimize the risks involved. Almost every tour operator set such a plan to get out of this disaster (Abbas, 2021).

The economy might be recovered after the pandemic by taking some precautionary measures such as positively promoting tourism, promoting new schemes, promotions, packages, and discounts to attract the masses, virtual marketing & economic packages best way to overcome the loss. As recovery from the pandemic is a gradual process so recovery of affected industries is also gradually possible in multiple phases (Valensi & Mohammad, 2021).

4.1. Theoretical implications

The theoretical contribution of this study is the themes that can be discussed further as valuable factors in future research. There are eight themes in the study related to decline in demand, revenue loss, unemployment of service staff, self-preparation, economic recovery plans, and opportunities that should be available. This study also contributes to the existing literature on pandemics.

During crises, proper communication should be placed to employees, the government, and stakeholders also. Crises planning and management for three perspectives government, trainers and industry need to prepare. Managers are strongly advised to communicate in a formal way with employees and use digitalization and motivate the tourists by offering specials during lean season and it is also an opportunity for managers to take advantage of the current

situation. It is the most appropriate and frequent way and also avoids physical contact which will reduce the health crises also (Gössling & Scott, 2020).

4.2. Practical implications

The most prominent themes in the study were the unemployment of service staff and the preparation to be benefitted from ongoing disasters. All the companies have experts who give suggestions to cope with the external environment in case of any disaster. During the Covid-19 pandemic, owners of the tourism and hospitality industry expel the service staff because of huge revenue loss. Instead of their retirement, companies should use multitasking. Because multitasking is the most latent solution to reduce redundancy and supply jobs for the additional staff. Organizations allot them with additional responsibilities and it also would be the norm of the tourism and the hospitality industry. Previous research (Kyriakidou&Maroudas, 2010) also indicates that this can be achieved by allotting them additional responsibilities to retain useful staff in the lean session and during low demand.

In the current time period, managers and the experts of the industry need to learn for themselves and the betterment of industry and government to minimize the revenue loss and damages in this ongoing event and similar pandemic may make reappeared and the voices gaining momentum of such affected situation. And it is also published in the previous research (Jamal & Budke, 2020).

Due to fluctuate in the tourists' behavior and understanding in the context to develop the strategies to provide the measures for the recovery of the industry after the pandemic is over. This study could use as the practical implications for the recovery and deal with such disaster if reappeared. The results are the same inline as the previous researches showed and it also revealed the current situation of the tourism and hospitality industry (Ben, 2020).

4.3. Limitations of the study and Future Research Suggestions

There are a few limitations in this study. Due to limited resources, the data could not be collected from the whole of the country. This leaves a gap in the study. Therefore, future researchers can collect data from other parts of Pakistan in order to generalize the results. The Covid-19 pandemic limited the scope of the study. Particularly researchers face great difficulty in the data collection process. Due to SOPs of the Covid-19 pandemic, the respondents feel hesitant to meet and to provide information. The future researcher can focus on some more research in the more geographical areas of Pakistan.

5. Conclusion

With the rise of the Covid-19 pandemic, there were several problems that occurred in the tourism and hospitality industry which affected negatively both the GDP and economy of the country. These several problems caused a decline in demand. Unemployment, revenue loss (potential and actual), travel restrictions, social distancing, etc. can be regarded as the foremost examples of these problems. Before Covid-19, the tourism and hospitality industry was contributing to the economy and GDP both nationally and internationally. Another main problem of the industry was that the industry didn't have strategic plans to cope with the external environment even before pandemic conditions. Along with the Covid-19 pandemic conditions, these uncertainty and ambiguity issues have increased highly.

This detailed study has resulted that the Covid-19 pandemic has caused a drastic decline in demand in the tourism and hospitality industry due to lockdown, ban on tourism, lack of funds, safety, and health issues. Peoples were fear of the situation because the situation is an anomaly. Not much is known about how to deal with such a disaster. Covid-19 threats, health issues, and travel restrictions imposed by the government, tourism, and hospitality industry bear a huge revenue loss. Due to the non-availability of funds and revenue loss(potential and actual) daily wagger staff, many tour guides, waiters, tour operators, became unemployed and Due to quarantine, social distancing, health consciousness, peoples prefer to stay at home and also due to decrease in purchasing power, tourism and hospitality industry affected negatively.

When disaster appears in the world, there were no strategic plans to cope with the situation. But businesses need to change their operation patterns. The economy can be recovered after a pandemic by taking some precautionary measures and by special offerings such as promotions, organizing new schemes, packages, discounts, virtual marketing. Covid-19 not only impacted negatively but also provided many opportunities like a clean environment, digitalized operating system and world move towards more innovations. To cope with such a pandemic needs to learn about more than one skill, managers need to work on themselves and through multitasking need to allot different responsibilities to reduce the redundancy and to secure the human resource after lean season and need to make sound plans and use adequate resources to meet consumers need and should have multiple income sources. Results of this study could use as the practical implications for the recovery and deal with such disaster if reappeared.

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Appendix
Table 1 interview findings

Themes	Sub-themes	Interview quotations	Interview numbers
Decline in demand and patronage	There is sharp demand decline in tourism and hospitality industry	“Covid-19 pandemic has caused drastic decline in demand in tourism and hospitality industry due to lockdown, ban on tourism, lack of funds, safety and health issues.”	14
Revenue loss	Tourism and Hospitality industry suffers revenue loss due to Covid-19 pandemic	“Due to COVID-19 threats, health issues, and travel restrictions imposed by government, tourism and hospitality industry beard a huge revenue loss.”	16
Unemployment of service staff	Covid-19 pandemic cause unemployment of service staff	“Due to prevalence of Covid-19, daily wager staff, many tour guides, waiters, tour operators, became unemployed due to lockdown and revenue loss.”	10
Travel restriction and social distancing	There is negative effect of Travel restriction and social distancing on industry due to Covid-19	“Due to quarantine, social distancing, health consciousness, peoples prefer to stay at home and also due to decrease in purchasing power, tourism and hospitality industry affected negatively.”	16
Strategic plans to deal with disaster	There are strategic plans to deal with Covid-19 pandemic	“When disaster appears in the world, there was no strategic plans to cope with the situation. But businesses needs to change their operation patterns...”	13
Economic recovery plans	There are suitable economic recovery plans after Covid-19 pandemic over	“Economy can be recover after pandemic by taking some precautionary measure and by special offerings such as promotions, organizing new schemes, packages, discounts, virtual marketing.’	10
Opportunities after pandemic over	There are many great opportunities foreseen after pandemic over	“Covid-19 not only impacted negatively but also provided many opportunities like clean environment, digitalize operating system and world move towards more innovations.”	15
Preparation to get advantage	Prepare to take advantage from opportunities that arise in result of Covid-19	“To cope with such pandemic, needs to learn about more than one skill, making sound plans and use adequate resources to meet consumers need and should have multiple income sources.”	17